

Reflections on the experience of initiation
Twenty-two testimonies of Freemasons
AASR ritual: extracts concerning initiation
Masonic song, opus 4, n ° 1, "When I was in the cave."

Réflexions sur le vécu de l'initiation
Recueil de 22 témoignages de francs-maçons
Rituel REAA: extraits concernant l'initiation
Chant maçonnique, opus 4, n°1, "Quand j'étais dans la caverne"

Sebök Ferenc, 2020

Initiation is a unique experience in the life of a Freemason. Indeed, being received a Freemason goes through a Masonic ritual, in a lodge, during which the candidate receives the light.

This is the symbolic pathway of profane life to death, including a cave or a Chamber of reflection, and concerning his initiation, then making three journeys. The candidate thus goes from death to life by receiving light and thus becoming an initiate. He becomes a new brother recognized as such by his brothers, joining the universal chain of existing brothers on the surface of the earth. It is interesting to try to know the feeling of a newly initiated brother, to collect the testimony concerning the experience of initiation.

This research work concerns testimonies from Freemasons to whom three questions were asked:

Is the experience of your initiation communicable?

What was your feeling during your initiation?

How did you experience the initiation?

The goal was the following: through the testimonies of Freemasons, try to better understand the impact of an initiation on the new initiate and to know if it is possible for him to reveal what happened to him and how the initiation was experienced. We hope to better understand the symbolic impact of initiation.

This research work contains large extracts from the ancient and accepted Scottish ritual so that the reader can understand the context and the links between testimonies and extracts from the ritual. To enrich the research, a painting concerning the Chamber of reflection will be presented, as well as a Masonic song concerning initiation.

22 testimonies are to be read, with the transcription of the answers to the three questions asked.

At the request of most brothers, anonymity has been guaranteed.

Noticed:

T1, T2,... T22 are the numbering of testimonies. The date indicates the year of the Freemason initiation.

T1, 1998

The experience of an initiation is very personal and therefore difficult to communicate, because impressions are difficult to understand out of context. To communicate, to testify cannot make faithfully what has been felt and experienced. There is therefore a good part of the secret in us. I experienced initiation with a certain stress, especially with the headband and the pathway in the Chamber of reflection, where symbols seemed to wonder.

I couldn't have an answer to everything. The writing of my philosophical will was difficult for me, because it was as if I had to write a will before dying.

My feeling was mixed. I said to myself at one point:

"But what do I do there, and why do it? ».

But my wish to go further took over and I was initiated. The three journeys were quite painful because I couldn't see anything and I felt pretty helpless, because I felt like I was undergoing events.

T2, 1998

I think the initiation is experienced differently by each of us and our reactions to what is happening too. The preparation of the outgoing candidate of Chamber of reflection is a bit impressive, because the candidate does not know what will happen. The unknown always generates stress when we don't have an answer. We must be guided and confidence must be born to continue the path of initiation.

As I am a very visual person, not knowing where I was putting my feet with a headband on my eyes crossed me a lot. During the three journeys, I did not understand the relationship between what I heard and what I was done. But other than that, I was serene, because I knew that my godfather was present.

After initiation, a feeling of well-being invaded my mind.

T3, 1999

Difficult to say my feelings because of the richness of the event and the phases of initiation, where, blindfolded, I do not master space or time, ultimately. After the initiation yes, the mind clad in and first answers appear, but faithfully communicate my experience and my impressions are difficult.

According to the sentences heard, I felt like I was a little in a court, because at times, the voices rose, quite threatening, sometimes dissuasive. Then being tossed with bandaged eyes created a kind of insecurity felt. I who don't drink often, the drink I had to drink had effect on me, because I had to drink everything without seeing anything. During the third journey, silence appeased me somewhat, which contrasted with silence in the Chamber of reflection. The Chamber of reflection was quite painful, because I was there, it seems, long enough. I was trying to understand the meaning of the signs, the skull, the elements present and the texts.

At the time of the headband removal, the light was quite aggressive after being plunged into the dark. I understood that it was the transition from darkness to light, coexisting with death followed by the Renaissance.

T4, 1999

We can try to tell what happened, but it is practically incommunicable, myself, I cannot faithfully speak my impressions and my experience in relation to the various phases of initiation. On the other hand, it is an intimate experience, difficult to explain or quite understandable by others.

It's as if we are trying to feel the same things as a mother who loses her child: incommunicable, but we can understand her pain.

I can say that several phases impressed me. For example, the Chamber of reflection where loneliness invaded me, while I hate loneliness. Certain elements present in this dark room, where I had to share the space with a skull, the deciphered texts, which sometimes seemed threatening, the oath I had to take. The swords pointed at me ... all of this was quite impressive.

What seemed difficult to live with me was also the first journey where the din seemed threatening. A feeling of well-being invaded me when I was integrated into the chain of union.

T5, 1999

My feelings? I panicked a little, a little stressed to have a headband. I didn't see anything anymore. Be blind, it must be terrible! We no longer master the space and even the passing time is no longer well under control. We finally discover the importance of visual sense. But I made the effort to dominate my fears and I let myself be guided by the one who received me when I hit the door of the Lodge.

Is my initiation communicable? It's difficult, because these are personal impressions and what we perceive is perhaps subjective in part. Then there are so many things that are jostling in the mind that it is difficult to remember everything, or to establish a certain chronology.

We had to attend another initiation to understand the context a little better and try, perhaps in vain, to understand what happens in the mind of the one who lives his initiation. The

experience must certainly be different. This means that for me, an initiation is personal and undoubtedly incommunicable.

In any case, when entering the lodge, I expected to be received with open arms ... and no, the tests were rather hard to pass. However, when I saw the light and I was in the chain of union, I felt intense appeasement.

T6, 2000

What was very difficult for me is the three journeys, especially the first: go through a small pathway then without being able to see anything, undergo intense noises. It was quite stressful. The Chamber of reflection, curiously did not give me stress at all, but rather a lot of curiosity: questions without many answers. But I told myself that I will probably have answers later.

My feelings are difficult to tell, because it is different depending on the various stages. However, I can say that I was quite confident, because I knew that my godfather was present somewhere. I think that for all profanes, the initiation tests must be lived and felt personally. It is therefore difficult to compare and tell this experience.

T7, 2000

What impressed me was the Chamber of reflection: I absolutely did not expect to find myself alone in a cramped place with a skull, a rooster, alchemical symbols, rather discouraging texts for someone who wants to be a member of this fraternity.

What also impressed me was the text of the ritual. Indeed, I saw nothing and I only had the ears to try to understand what was going on. Another sensory capacity could also reassure me when I was touched and guided me; I trusted, but the first trip was the hardest to pass.

What also impressed me were the warnings, the sentences sometimes quite hostile, then more reassuring. Maillet blows in three different places also impressed me. My feeling was quite mixed until the headband was removed, to put it back afterwards. This first visual perception of the temple soothed me. What was also impressive are the swords turned towards me. I understood at that time what the word "being perjury" could mean.

T8, 2000

I think that personal experience, we can tell it, but understanding by others will be parcelled anyway, because the impressions are personal and the impressions, the perceptions vary according to the individuals. I think it is in this context that it is incommunicable.

The different stages impressed me: the Chamber of reflection that led me to try to understand what surrounded me, without being able to understand too much. Then will I have been asked to write, because I did not know what to write, then I was able to find ideas to write. My swearing in I impressed me a lot as well as the dubbing.

Finally, the chain of union in which the brothers integrated me. At that time I had the impression that I was finally part of a great fraternity.

T9, 2000

What impressed me a lot was the firm of reflection where I imagined myself going back in time ... almost in the time of the alchemists! Then my experience was painful enough for two reasons: the fact that I saw nothing and I had to make a big effort to listen and try to understand. But despite my efforts, what the actors told was very difficult to understand, because too symbolic, and that made me think a little that I was in the space-time of another age.

The impressions felt are too personal and numerous to be able to tell them exhaustively. Yes, it is incommunicable, because what we can tell is fragmented and the other people to whom I would tell all the emotions would perceive them in a different way.

T10,2008

Already trying to faithfully tell everything that happened is difficult. So it seems to me that initiation, even if I tell it to someone, is incommunicable. It's a personal experience and that's why it's a secret.

The writing of my philosophical testament will make me feel like someone who was going or who was to die. The skull also suggested that to me. Reading what was written around me seemed to want to discourage the one who would come there as a tourist, or someone who would be little motivated. The three journeys were enigmatic for me, even if each time we explained the meaning.

In fact, the events rushed and I didn't have time to understand everything. I felt pretty helpless at times, but what was reassuring was the fact that I felt guided by someone benevolent. Bengal fire with the swords pointed at me very much impressed me. Feeling the point of something on my chest was also quite striking.

T11, 2008

I remember the essential that has remained in my head regarding the day of my initiation. The Chamber of reflection plunged me into a solitude where I had understood that was not alone, but with myself in a way. At the beginning, it was challenging, but as I stayed there long, it

became a little stressful, since I imagined lots of things, without having any answers. The fact that a brother returned to me broke this solitude becoming inconvenient.

The initiation ritual, on the other hand, seemed to me quite fun, like a discovery in stages that we commented on. I was still quite serene. The light that blinded me impressed me, especially when I discerned unknown faces around me pointing their finger or their sword.

I think my experience is not quite communicable, because these are many emotions and feelings that are not always easy to express with words.

T12, 2008

What impressed me were the words and sentences written in the Chamber of reflection, as well as the alchemical elements. I was wondering a little where it all was going to lead me, especially since I am someone rational.

The three journeys seemed to me quite theatrical, without my knowing where I was going since I had blinded eyes. However, I felt that I was walked in circles. Fortunately, the explanations accompanied the wanderings. However, I did not understand little, so much, so much have been said.

I think I can easily tell the different stages, but it is difficult or impossible to talk about your emotions and say how initiation was experienced. It is all the more true that it is difficult to remember all the steps. Yes, the experience, what is removed is personal. Even by telling the experience, the question is how others will perceive what you say.

T13, 2007

Having experienced initiation remains engraved in my mind, even after four years of masonry. There are elements of the experience that are unspeakable; And even shortly after, we ask ourselves questions, so how could we tell questions or emotions. I have perceived things, but I am sure that others may have perceived things differently, or perceived different things.

Walking was not easy for me because of my age and the fact that I easily lose my balance. But I felt that I was well guided and I trusted, even blindfolded. The chain of union and the oath impressed me.

T14, 2008

During the three journeys, I really thought of a play where I was the main actor, but silent and blind. The three that I remained was the taste, because I was made to drink an alcoholic liquid, the tactile meaning, because I was guided and I felt the water, air and heat, therefore

fame and I listened to what we said. It was quite destabilizing. But I trusted because I knew several people who were in the temple.

It is difficult to tell the experience, what we felt because there are too many things and it is difficult to tell faithfully. And then we also forget, but initiation is a significant event in Masonic life. Yes, I think-lived experience is difficult to communicate.

T15, 2008

Writing my will was difficult because, if at first I did not know what to write, after several minutes, I had too many ideas and I still didn't know what to write. Finally, I wrote the latest ideas I had, knowing that it was only partially that I had filled my will. I do not know certain symbols and what challenged me is the rooster, the hourglass and a text inviting the one that comes out of curiosity, to leave.

I understood that the skull referred to death, as well as my will. This analogy led me to think that the skull could be mine. The first journey was quite stressful, even if we were guided, the sounds heard strengthened the feeling of insecurity.

The third journey and the chain of union were soothing. The dubbing with the sword was also impressive. The feelings and the feelings are difficult to communicate ... At most, we can say certain things, but not everything and anyway, another will experience initiation in another way.

T16, 2010

My experience in the Chamber of reflection is a very intense moment full of emotions. It is difficult to communicate, as experience is intense. In addition, this passage is followed by the three journey, the swearing in, consecration as an Entered Apprentice.

The pointed swords, the compass on the heart, the destabilizing headband, the chain of union are all experiences rich in symbolism and I think that perceptions and understanding of things belong to each of us and it is personal.

A feeling of belonging to a fraternity going beyond the lodge and the borders invaded me and I did not regret having taken the plunge. But the Lodge had warned me of the long and difficult journey that awaited me.

T17, 2010

What can I say except that in my Masonic life, the two most striking events were my initiation and when I was received as a master mason. Whatever the event experienced, it is very personal and almost incommunicable, because it is charged with emotions, perceptions.

Each time, a rich ritual leads the mason to think, to understand. The questioning is a necessity to progress. The loneliness in the cave with the skull and the alchemical elements were elements quite enigmatic for me. What was written seemed to try to dissuade unwelcome.

For my part, I was well decided to become a Freemason, because I know a few and I was able to judge their qualities of men. The oath and the consecration as an apprentice made me think very much.

T18, 2018

What was rich for me is that it was a double initiation. So I had a twin brother in the making. The things that have challenged me are the elements present in the Chamber of reflection. Then the three journeys, the first one was quite stressful. Then the brothers' chain of union providing a kind of feeling of well-being.

The moment to see the light with the swords pointed at me was impressive. Finally, after initiation, during fraternal feasts, the sharing was quite magical. I really felt integration into the lodge and the "toasts" were memorable for me, because beyond seriousness in the execution of rituals, in the feasts, the brothers showed their human side, tender and jovial.

Telling all of this to a layman is impossible, because it must have lived it to be able to share experiences.

T19, 2018

My initiation is made up of somewhat difficult times. For instance, the fairly long solitude in the Chamber of reflection, but fortunately, the brother who guided me in my steps was very fraternal and therefore I trusted.

I also knew two people as members of the Lodge. The three journeys went without too much difficulty or apprehension. On the other hand, I really wondered what I was going to write on my will and I was wondering what we were going to do with it. Doubt assaulted me: what to write? ... I chose to be "real", without hiding anything.

I didn't particularly like the drink I had to drink, but, on the other hand, after the initiation, the meal called "fraternal feasts" was delicious.

Bad striking moments? The first journey, because I had blindfolded and I saw nothing and with the din and wandering by losing the balance sometimes, I was wondering what was going to happen to finish. The other two trips soothed me.

When I was removed the headband, the light was very lively and it took me a while to discern the swords turned towards me ... It was impressive.

The experience of initiation is very personal and I imagine that everyone can perceive things in a different way. Therefore, there is a form of "incommunicability".

T20, 2020

I was quite stressed because I left my work and I was late because of the road. Arrived on site, someone clothed in an apron, opened me with a kind smile that removed my stress. I felt much better.

I quickly wrote my philosophical testament, with erasures. I was feverish because I was stressed again. I was sweating and looked at an interrogator when I saw the skull, the skeleton with the skull.

Finally, I was able to finish my will when the brother mason returned to me. He immediately felt my stress and reassured me by putting his hand on my shoulder saying: "Don't worry, everything will be fine."

Concerning the three journeys : however, passed in a more serene way, even with a headband on the eyes. The ready -made oath made me think and I was trying to measure its importance. When the Worshipful master took his flaming sword to devote as an Entered Apprentice, I was serene, with a certain pride. Fraternal feasts are unforgettable for me.

T21, 2020

Initiation is an unforgettable thing overall, but it is very difficult to remember everything. The impressions, however, remained as well as the emotions that the various stages of initiation caused me. All this is difficult to communicate.

The Chamber of reflection is a moment of solitude and unforgettable silence: I find myself in front of myself.

The striking moments are the different journey, especially the first, the oath and the dubbing as an apprentice mason.

T22, 2021

The experience of initiation is unforgettable and belongs to each mason who has been able to perceive things in a very personal way.

The initiation contains the chamber of reflection where the candidate must be alone. Then, in the temple, the fact of making three journeys followed by the dubbing and the closure of the lodge were impressive.

Fraternal feasts so-called « Harmony » or « Agapes » are witness to a very simple fraternity, but true and contrast with the seriousness involved in the ritual of the initiation ceremony. I have a very positive memory of it.

End of testimonies.

Here is an example of a Tracing Board concerning the Chamber of reflection.

Chamber of Reflection, 100x70, 2011, Ink and acrylic on cardboard, Ferenc Sebök.

Now a musical composition concerning initiation, and especially, the song of the candidate being in the cave (firm of reflection):

Opus 4, n ° 1 "When I was in the cave", Ferenc Sebök.

Adaptation for voice and piano of opus 4, n ° 1 of collection A, "Duos for violins", work published by Van de Velde (Lemoine), Paris, Ferenc Sebök.

Reference: VV273, ISBN/ISMN 9790560052731.

There are a total of four collections. Collections B, C and D have as a reference:

VV 274, VV275, VV276 - ISBN/ISMN 9790560052748 - ISBN/ISMN 9790560052755 - ISBN/ISMN 9790560052762

<https://www.henry-lemoine.com/fr/partitions-pour-ensemble/17221-miroirs-de-styles-recueil-b.html>

The words in Masonic singing speak of the candidate's path in the “cave”, and his emotions.

Quand j'étais dans la caverne Op.4 n°1

Ferenc Sebök

$\bullet = 48$

Voix

Quand j'étais dans la ca-ver-ne mon coeur serré mais a-ler-te je me di-sais qu'il fait sombre avec ce crâ-ne dans l'ombre

Piano

mp

5

Voix

Ma peur pri-me sur ma passion et mon coeur crie la rai-son de ma présence en ce bas monde si je savais le mot des dieux

Piano

mf *mp* *mf*

9

Voix

j'è-cri rais mieux mon tes-ta-ment toute ma pensée secret de l'âme que je ca-che je me blâ-me mais que faire pour é-tre vrai

Piano

mf

13

Voix

è-tre moi même sortir d'ici l'esprit tranquille de voir le temps qui se défile et j'ai besoin de la lu-mi-ère

Piano

mp

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17

Voix

la gorge serrée vi - triol que dois-je faire a-vec ce coq so-li-tai-re qui m'ob-ser-ve si je savais le mot des dieux

Piano

mf

mf

21

Voix

je comprendrais l'at-mos-phé-re toute ma pensée secret de l'âme que je ca-che je me blâ-me mais que faire pour é - tre vrai

Piano

mf

25

Voix

é - tre moi-même sortir d'ici l'esprit tranquille de voir le temps qui se défile et j'ai besoin de la lu - mi - ère

Piano

mp

29

Voix

Quand j'étais dans la ca-ver-ne mon coeur serré mais a-ler-te je me disais qu'il fait sombre avec ce crâ - ne dans l'ombre

Piano

mp

Reflection on these testimonies.

The testimonies go in the same without with regard to the communicability of the initiation. Among some candidates, fear existed at the beginning, but confidence took over. The testimonies highlight different experiences, different impressions and the event provokes various personal emotions which are considered difficult to tell concerning initiation.

Testimonials highlight stress in some, questioning and misunderstanding certain elements or certain stages.

The Chamber of reflection has somewhat impressed the candidates. The oath and dubbing marked the spirits of some, as well as the pointed swords and the light for others. Light also seems to have impressed the candidates.

Initiation is a process that accompanies the mason throughout its journey. Several candidates highlight the feeling of well-being during the dubbing, taking part in the chain of union and during the fraternal feasts.

Initiation is not a punctual event. Indeed, once the light was received by the candidate, he is recognized as a Freemason by his brothers in a solemn way. But this initiation to the rank of Entered Apprentice will be followed by two other blue lodges which works for the three degrees of Entered apprentice, Fellow craft and master.

Concerning the ancient and accepted Scottish rite, the High degrees go to the 30th degree called "Kadosch knight », not to mention the administrative grades (31 °, 32 ° and 33 °). According to different rites, the number of degrees varies. For example, at the Memphis-Misraïm rite, there are even 99 degrees. But this work is confined to the degrees of the blue lodge.

The different degrees are initiations. I prefer to speak of “initiation extension”. The preparation of the candidate is essential.

Here is an extract from the ritual of the r ° L ° Les Vrais Amis, 51, GLRB: (in French)

INITIATION

Preparation of the Profane.

Provide in the Chamber of reflection: the table, a cut with salt, a cut with suffering, a piece of bread a candle, a few sheets of paper and what to write.

In the Chamber of reflection the profane will be invited to write his philosophical will.

When I introduce him into the Lodge, the expert prepares the candidate in the traditional way:

- *withdrawal of all metals;*
- *bare head;*
- *Naked left breast and arm;*

- *Naked right knee;*
- *Differentiated left foot;*
- *headband on the eyes;*
- *Cord to the neck.*

The « metals » of the profane will be entrusted to the Brother Almoner.

Noticed:

The "metals" or personal objects will be returned after the candidate's initiation.

Then, the master Brother of the ceremonies will welcome the candidate outside the temple and tell him what follows (AASR ritual):

**Reception of the candidate upon arrival by the brother master of the ceremonies.
Read outside the temple.**

Sir,

I am responsible for receiving you.

I want to tell you that you are in an environment which, as of now, grants you its sympathy.

The use wants you to have blindfolded.

Please, please put this headband yourself, showing that you do it for your free will.

Please what no light touches your eyes.

Now let yourself go with confidence.

Noticed:

The master of ceremonies leads the candidate in the "cave" (Chamber of reflection).

The candidate being in the « Cave » no longer has his headband and can see what surrounds him when he is alone. After a while, the expert brother will come to him and say the following (according to the AASR ritual):

**Reception of the candidate in the immediate master past.
Read before the start of the Masonic Meeting.**

Sir,

You asked to be admitted to Freemasonry.

I guess you have considered all the consequences of your decision, and that you know that you will link to us by irrevocable commitments.

We will not ask you, moreover, nothing that can be accepted by a probed and free man.

Sir, traditional and universal Freemasonry is an organization having a clean origin which cannot be confused with that of religions, without, however, doing a profession of atheism.

It leaves everyone on its freedom of thought, and, although stable in its principle, it knows how to adapt to the circumstances of time and places.

Organization of immemorial origin, it develops its teachings in a symbolic form.

Do not be surprised if some of our customs may seem obsolete or archaic.

You will only be ours if, on this occasion, your mind gets rid of everything it can contain prejudice and errors.

In any initiation, the use wants candidates to strip objects of metal which they relate to them. To make sensitive what must be accomplished in you spiritually, I beg you to put all the metal objects that you wear on you.

Please now

Carefully fill in the following document ...

Noticed :

It is his philosophical testament will that he must write.

Then comes the next step where the candidate is prepared before introducing it into a lodge by a "low door" (if necessary by passing it under a bar prepared for this purpose).

The Expert brother addresses the candidate before bringing him to the forecourt of the temple and will tell him what follows:

**Reception of the candidate by the Expert brother.
Read before the lodge introduction.**

Sir, time has come!

The trials of initiation include a very deep spiritual meaning.

They refer to the transformations which must be accomplished in you, if, really you aspire to become a man worthy of participating in a new life.

During the ceremony that will take place, let yourself be dominated by your emotions.

You will not understand anything by reasoning.

Emotion will lead you to inner vision, a source of your strength.

And the lodge ritual thus begins (AASR):

V :.M.:

Mes Frères, l'ordre du jour de nos Travaux appelle l'initiation au grade d'Apprenti Maçon du Profane (prénom et nom), qui a fait l'objet de trois scrutins favorables.

F.: Trésorier, ce Profane est-il en règle de métaux?

F.: Très.: Oui, V.:M.:

V.:M.: F.: Expert, ce Profane est-il dans le Cabinet de Réflexion?

Expert Oui, V.:M.:

V.:M.: Puisqu'il en est ainsi, F.: Expert, allez vers le Profane et ramenez-moi son Testament.

... Then the ritual continues as follows:

V.:M.: F.: Expert, retournez vers le Profane, accordez sa vêtue et amenez-le à la porte de la Loge au F.:Maître des cérémonies.

... Then the ritual continues as follows:

Couvreur Qui frappe ainsi ?

M.:d.:C.: C'est un Profane qui demande l'entrée de la Loge.

Couvreur C'est un Profane qui demande l'entrée de la Loge, F.: 2^d Surv.:..

2^d Surv.: C'est un Profane qui demande l'entrée de la Loge, F.:1^{er} Surv.:..

1^{er} Surv.: C'est un Profane qui demande l'entrée de la Loge V.:M.:..

V.:M.: Comment ose-t-il l'espérer F.:1^{er} Surv.: ?

1^{er} Surv.: Comment ose-t-il l'espérer F.:2^d Surv.: ?

2^d Surv.: Comment ose-t-il l'espérer F.: Couvr.: ?
Couvreur Comment ose-t-il l'espérer ?
M.:d.:C.: Parce que c'est un homme né libre et de bonnes mœurs.
Couvreur Parce que c'est un homme né libre et de bonnes mœurs, F.: 2^d Surv.:.
2^d Surv.: Parce que c'est un homme né libre et de bonnes mœurs, F.: 1^{er} Surv.:.
1^{er} Surv.: Parce que c'est un homme né libre et de bonnes mœurs, V.: M.:.

...

V.:M.: Monsieur (prénom, nom), que voyez-vous, que sentez-vous?

M.:d.:C.: (souffleur des réponses au profane)

Prof.: Je ne vois rien, mais je sens la pointe d'une arme.

V.:M.: Cette arme est l'image du remords qui déchirerait votre cœur si vous deveniez parjure envers la société dans laquelle vous demandez à être admis. Le bandeau qui couvre vos yeux souligne l'aveuglement de l'homme dominé par ses passions et plongé dans l'ignorance.
Monsieur, que voulez-vous de nous ?

Prof.: Je demande à être reçu franc-maçon.

V.:M.: Est-ce de votre propre volonté, sans nulle contrainte et en pleine liberté que vous vous présentez à nous ?

Prof.: oui.

V.:M.: Réfléchissez bien, Monsieur, à la démarche que vous faites. Elle peut vous mener à subir des épreuves qui exigent toute la fermeté du caractère le plus décidé.

Etes-vous bien décidé à les subir ?

Worshipful Master : Sir, put yourself in your knee and take part in the invocation that we will send to the supreme being, a great architect of the universe.

The Expert Brother helps the candidate to kneel and remains on his left.

Worshipful Master : To order my brothers!

Let us include before the great architect of the universe; Let us recognize its power and our weakness; Let us satisfy our minds and our hearts in the limits of equity and let's get rid of up to him. He is one, he exists by himself. Let him deign to protect the workers of peace, animate their zeal, fill their hearts with the love of virtue. That he helps their success and that of this aspirant who wishes to participate in our august mysteries. Give him his assistance, and aids him in the midst of the trials he will undergo. Amen.

Take your seat, my brothers!

V.:M.: Profane, en qui mettez-vous votre confiance ?

Prof.: (Le F.:Exp.: souffle la réponse) En Dieu !

V.:M.: Puisque vous placez votre confiance en Dieu, Suivez la main qui vous guide et ne craignez aucun danger. Persistez-vous dans votre désir d'être reçu franc-maçon ?

Prof.: (Le F.:Exp.: souffle) «OUI»

V.:M.: Monsieur, je vous le dis une dernière fois: s'il vous reste quelque scrupule, quelque répugnance, vous êtes libre de vous retirer.

Mais je vous en avertis, bientôt vous ne le
pourrez plus.
Persistez-vous dans votre désir d'être reçu
franc-maçon ?

Prof.: oui

V.:M.:

1^{er} Surv.:

2nd Surv.:

V.:M.: Frère Expert, emparez-vous du Profane.
Faites-lui faire le 1^{er} voyage.

(Worshipful Master : Brother Expert, get the profane and make him the 1st trip).

As a reminder, here are the three degrees of the blue lodge and more specific remarks concerning the degree of Entered apprentice.

The first degree is the degree of apprentice, the second degree is that of the companion who will make five trips and will discover, especially the "letter G" as well as "the flamboyant star". The third trip is the ultimate degree of the blue lodge, that of the master, where the companion will live the "legend of Hiram".

This work focuses on the first degree of apprentice with the testimony of brothers. The candidate makes a spontaneous request where he is co-opted thanks to the help of a Freemason. A long process starts, which lasts about a year to a year and a half.

Investigators will be appointed by the venerable master, in the Middle Chamber (r ° L ° Sambre and Meuse, Modern Belgian Rite, GLRB and R ° L ° The real friends, Old and Accepted Scottish Rite, GLRB).

After the path under the headband, brethren vote by black and white balls, by a secret vote. In case the vote is positive, a date is decided by the venerable master.

The path through the Chamber of reflection where the candidate will be invited to go will be for him a place and a moment when he faces symbols, elements, a skull, inscriptions on the

wall or on panels. Sometimes a painting exists in the lodge, presenting a synthesis of the elements of the Chamber of reflection.

In the Chamber of reflection, the candidate writes his philosophical testament which will be brought by the Expert brother at the end of his sword, in the lodge. He will transmit it to the Worshipful master who will transmit him to the orator brother for reading to the Lodge brothers.

In some lodges, the testament is burned in a lodge (W°L° The seven pillars, GLRB).

Once introduced into the temple with blindfolded eyes, the important will undergo three trips where he will undergo the test of air, water, fire. Finally, he will take an oath, then receive the light, removing the headband. It was at this point that the new initiate will see brothers around him pointing to a sword towards him.

This symbolism is explained to him by the Worshipful master (according to the ritual). Initiation has a "sacred" character for Freemasonry and the oath lent and the fact of helping his brothers in distress : all these things are not only commitments, but are part of this "sacred character" which is important for Freemasons.

In practice, it is a shame to note that the oaths ready are sometimes broken and the commitments not kept.

In these cases, the brother is perjury and the question is whether it is still a "Brother recognized as such by his brothers" (AASR ritual). The three journeys must occur experience.

During the first journey, the din produced by the brothers alludes to profane life, but also to the difficulties of daily life, it alludes to our passions which must be overcome to walk in the royal way where the mason must look for the Light (in him) to be able to discern things, take a step back by practicing introspection and looking for the truth.

During this first trip, he feels the "water" element is a symbol of purification (baptism uses the same symbolism).

Then, during the second trip, he will go through the test of "the air" reminiscent of "Ruah", the creative and life breath.

Finally, the profane will go through the "fire" test. This fire allows the transformation of the material into light, accompanied by a heat clearance.

And the ritual continues as follows:

V :. M :. Au cours de ce troisième voyage ont régné
 l'ordre, la paix et le silence. Ainsi en est-il
 dans la vie de l'homme qui a surmonté ses
 passions.

Monsieur, vos voyages sont heureusement terminés. Je ne saurais trop louer votre courage.

V.:M.: La persévérance de Monsieur (prénom et nom) est éprouvée. Que demandez-vous pour lui ?

1^{er} Surv.: Que le bandeau lui soit enlevé, qu'il voie et qu'il médite.

V.:M.: Qu'il en soit ainsi à mon coup de Maillet.

Mes Frères, debout ! Faites votre devoir !

V.:M.: (Quand le feu de Bengale est allumé)

V.:M.: Monsieur, ces sombres feux et ces glaives tournés vers vous vous annoncent que si vous trahissiez votre serment, vous ne trouveriez parmi les francs-maçons répandus sur la surface de la Terre que des vengeurs de la vertu.

V.:M.: Frère maître des Cérémonies, remettez-lui le bandeau.
Prenez place, mes Frères.

V.:M.: Monsieur, vous allez maintenant prêter votre Obligation solennelle sur les trois Grandes Lumières de la Franc-maçonnerie, qui sont le Volume de la Loi Sacrée, le Compas et l'Équerre. Frère Expert et Maître des Cérémonies, amenez le Profane devant l'autel.

... Then a little further the ritual continues as follows:

V.:M.: F.:2^d Surv.:, que demandez-vous pour le Profane?

2^d Surv.: La Lumière !

V.:M.: F.: 1^{er} Surv.:, que demandez-vous pour le Profane?

1^{er} Surv.: La Lumière !

V.:M.: Monsieur, que demandez-vous?

Prof.: (Le F.:Exp.: souffle) la Lumière

V.:M.: Que la Lumière soit, à mon 3^e coup de Maillet !

Then the venerable master will take the flaming sword to "create it", "devote it" and "receive it" Freemason from the Lodge. This ultimate step is made in front of the altar and the new initiate (called neophyte in the ritual) will be kneeling.

Then the newly initiated brother will receive his apron with a bib, white gloves, female gloves as well as the jewel of the lodge and a copy of the constitution of the obedience. He will also receive his first instruction. The ceremony will end with the "closing of the Lodge", followed by "fraternal feasts" (Harmony).

Freemasonry is therefore an initiatory journey which will extend to the rank of master and beyond, if the brother continues his evolution in the high ranks named « Ecosism ».

He can also choose other initiation ways such as "the royal arch", "the Red Cross of Constantine" or other existing ways, thanks to the existence of "side degrees". Initiation is the fundamental reason for the existence of Freemasonry, because without initiation, the Lodge is doomed to disappear.

The headband on the eyes and its wandering in the lodge guided by the expert brother, reminds the layman that he is in darkness and that he is looking for light. Initiation is done thanks to the timeless ritual, which is highly codified. The ritual is at the centre of Freemasonry, because without him, nothing could be done.

What do the laymen come to seek in Freemasonry? Brotherhood ?

Admittedly, but also the fact of being able to make progress in Freemasonry: an initiatory path of ignorance to knowledge, the culture of theological and cardinal values, for example, moving from selfishness to charity.

